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Registration Results, Patient 1 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 1 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 1 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 1 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 2 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 2 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 3 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 3 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 4 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 4 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 4 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 4 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 5 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 5 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 5 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 5 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 6 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 6 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 7 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 7 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 7 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 7 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 8 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 8 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 8 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 8 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 9 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 9 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 9 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 9 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 10 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 10 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 10 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 10 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 11 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 11 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 11 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 11 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 12 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 12 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 13 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 13 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 14 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 14 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 14 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 14 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 15 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 15 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 16 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 16 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 17 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 17 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 18 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 18 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 18 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 18 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 20 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 20 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 20 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 20 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 21 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 21 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 22 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 22 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 23 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 23 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 24 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 24 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 24 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 24 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 25 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 25 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 25 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 25 (right foot)



Registration Results, Patient 26 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 26 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 27 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 27 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 28 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 28 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 29 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 29 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 29 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 29 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 30 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 30 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 31 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 31 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 32 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 32 (right foot)



Registration Results, Patient 33 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 33 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 33 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 33 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 34 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 34 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 34 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 34 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 35 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 35 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 36 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 36 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 36 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 36 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 37 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 37 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 38 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 38 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 40 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 40 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 42 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 42 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 42 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 42 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 43 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 43 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 44 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 44 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 44 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 44 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 45 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 45 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 46 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 46 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 46 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 46 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 47 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 47 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 48 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 48 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 49 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 49 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 49 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 49 (right foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 50 (left foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 50 (left foot)



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Registration Results, Patient 50 (right foot)



Statistical Results, Patient 50 (right foot)



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